

University Marine Energy Research Community

2023 Conference

4-6 October | Durham, NH, USA

Great Lakes wave energy resource classification and Blue Economy opportunities

Chase Pheifer^{a,1}, Craig Hill^{a,b}

^aMechanical & Industrial Engineering, University of Minnesota Duluth, 1305 Ordean Ct., Duluth, MN 55812, USA

^bInstitute on the Environment, University of Minnesota, 1954 Buford Ave, St. Paul, MN 55108, USA

Abstract

Due to recent interest in the Laurentian Great Lakes (GL) offshore wind energy, availability of other marine energy resources also needs to be assessed following IEC (International Electrotechnical Commission) standards. Wave energy conversion has proven to contribute towards energy demands at small scales, particularly for Blue Economy industries. The GL have largely been overlooked in other assessments focusing on coastal waters, yet its marine resource presents opportunities and unique challenges for wave energy research and development, Blue Economy applications, and augmentation to United States and Canadian national energy resource and planning databases. This paper highlights seasonal and annual wave energy resource characteristics in the GL from a study calculating the spatial and temporal distributions of wave resource parameters following IEC standards and a recently developed coastal US wave energy resource classification system. Results focus on analysis from historical numerical modeling, specifically the GL Environmental Research Lab's implementation of the Donelan wave model in their GL Coastal Forecasting System from 2006-2020. This model data and NDBC buoy observations are used to estimate annual energy potential. Further emphasis is placed on the role the GL could play towards sustainably developing unique marine energy solutions for the Blue Economy, specifically by serving as a scaled field laboratory for wave energy conversion technology R&D. The analysis will focus on significant wave height, wave energy period, and omnidirectional deep water wave power. In terms of a recent coastal US wave power classification, more than 88% of GL Erie, Michigan, Ontario, and Superior and 72% of Lake Huron fall into Class III (Marginal) for wave power, and the rest of the GL surface area falls into Class IV (Poor); for peak period, all of the GL fall into Band 1. Similar to the coastal US, the GL wave energy resource is lower on average in the summer months vs. the winter months; for example, the average wave power in July from 2006-2020 over Lake Superior's entire surface is 0.33 kW/m vs. a December average of 4.3 kW/m. Though the Donelan wave model fails to meet the criteria (e.g., it does not consider sea ice, whitecapping, wave-current interactions, and water level variations, among others) for the IEC's most basic assessment level (Class 1—Reconnaissance), it performs well for such a coarse and simplistic model when compared to NDBC buoy observations and presents an opportunity for a first step towards a wide-spread assessment of the GL wave energy resource.

Keywords: wave energy resource assessment; Laurentian Great Lakes; Donelan wave model; Blue Economy

* Corresponding author

E-mail address: pheif003@d.umn.edu

1. Introduction

The Laurentian Great Lakes (GL) are the largest system of freshwater in the world and are surrounded by a population of over 30 million people who rely on these bodies of water for drinking water, jobs, and recreation [1]. The GL region would have the 3rd highest GDP in the world if it were its own country [2]. In recent years, interest in understanding the GL' potential for renewable energy production has grown beyond the small number of conventional and pumped storage hydropower plants in the region. Two recent reports have assessed the feasibility and opportunities for wind energy on the GL, and the Icebreaker offshore wind project on Lake Erie was recently approved by the Ohio Supreme Court in August 2022 [3–5]. If implemented successfully, the Icebreaker wind project is likely to accelerate other renewable energy projects on the GL. Given the Department of Energy's (DOE) recent marine energy initiative, Powering the Blue Economy™ (PBE), an assessment of wave energy resource characteristics for the GL is necessary, particularly because the US Marine Energy Atlas and a recent classification of the wave energy resource in the United States leave out the GL [6–8]. The recently developed US wave energy classification scheme includes four wave power classes: $22.8 < J$, Class I (Excellent); $5.7 < J < 22.8$, Class II (Good); $1.1 < J < 5.7$, Class III (Marginal), and $J < 1.1$, Class IV (Poor), where J is omnidirectional wave power in $\text{kW}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$; in addition to defining three wave period classification bands: $0 < T_p < 7$, Band 1; $7 < T_p < 10$, Band 2; and $10 < T_p$, Band 3, where T_p is the peak period in seconds [7]. These classification bands and classes present a straightforward way of comparing the wave energy resource in the GL to coastal US locations.

Challenging winter observation conditions on the GL limit our understanding of wave conditions during winter months, yet climatological trends are creating extended open water seasons with potential for large storm events and increases in wave energy potential. Though the wave energy resource on the GL is minimal during summer months, except for occasional storms, late fall and early spring storms are frequent and intense. One popular historical example is the infamous November 1975 storm which fatefully sunk the Edmund Fitzgerald amidst 7m waves, killing her crew of 29 members [9,10]. These storms often create millions of dollars of damage, so new approaches exploring innovative methods for harnessing wave energy along susceptible coastlines in the Great Lakes could provide opportunities for coastal PBE applications [11].

A significant focus of the developing marine energy industry emphasizes its role in PBE applications. This includes potential for powering observation equipment; desalination equipment; rapidly deployable or reliable baseload generation for remote, islanded communities; and onsite power for aquaculture operations, among many other emerging opportunities [6,12,13]. Many of these applications require lower power demands, and recent studies have emphasized the benefit of exploring low wave energy resource environments across the globe [14]. These low resource environments decrease the risk of deployments, provide opportunities to advance wave energy converter (WEC) technologies, and can readily provide power to a number of PBE applications. The Great Lakes region is potentially one location that offers lower resources yet promising opportunities for WEC R&D, though a comprehensive resource assessment is necessary to identify energy potential and key areas for targeting developmental activities. Additionally, the GL have a strong potential to serve as a scaled field laboratory for WECs, especially for potential Polar region deployments, given that ice regularly forms on the GL. They will also provide opportunities for advancing WECs for deployments in low energy seas [14]. This assessment seeks to build upon previous limited characterizations of the GL' wave energy by performing an assessment according to an internationally recognized standard for all five GL rather than one specific GL [15–17].

2. Methodology

In order for a wave energy assessment to be valid beyond one measurement location, *IEC TS 62600 - 101:2015 - Wave energy resource assessment and characterization* (hereafter referred to as the TS) requires that a spatially comprehensive data source with at least ten years of data be utilized [18]. To date, the only data source that fulfills those qualifications and is publicly available is the GL Environmental Research Lab's (GLERL) archive of the GL Coastal Forecasting System's implementation of the Donelan wave model [19,20]. This archive includes hourly wave data for each of the five GL with varying resolutions over a 2006-2020 period of record, with a transition to using the National Center for Environmental Prediction's WAVEWATCH III (WW3) model part way through 2021. The GLCFS implementation of the Donelan wave model (hereafter referred to as the Donelan) used the same structured grid as the GLCFS's implementation of the Princeton Ocean Model for the GL (Table 1). The output of the Donelan model provides only three wave parameters: significant wave height, wave direction, and wave period [21–23]. This model is currently the best comprehensive data source covering the surface of the GL. An *in-situ* source of GL wave

data comes from the National Data Buoy Center (NDBC) which deploys buoys throughout the GL, though these buoys are only deployed seasonally due to risk of damage from ice and storms. Recent wave energy resource assessments using historical data from nine GL NDBC buoys have been completed, yet these observation systems are typically only deployed for two-thirds of the year depending on location.

Table 1. GLCFS Donelan wave model grid summary

Lake	Period with complete data	Grid Size	Grid Cell Dimensions [km]	Number of grid cells > 0m depth	Grid cells > 0 m depth that are also > 16m depth [%]
Superior	2006-2020	61x30	10x10	807	98
Michigan	2006-2020	131x251	2x2	14458	86
Huron	2009-2020	201x188	2x2	14733	83
Erie	2006-2020	193x87	2x2	6436	63
Ontario	2006-2020	61x25	5x5	746	89

The TS is the international standard for an assessment of wave energy resources [18]. This TS has three classes of assessment: reconnaissance, feasibility, and design, with wave energy resource estimation uncertainty ranging from high to low, respectively. The TS outlines the necessary characteristics of the data source to fall into one of those three categories. The Donelan used for this analysis fails to meet the criteria for even the lowest fidelity assessment class (viz., reconnaissance), specifically because it does not directly model whitecapping, quadruplet interactions, diffraction, refraction, effects of sea ice, water level variations, wave reflections, or wave-current variations, all of which are required to be considered for the reconnaissance assessment class. The Donelan does meet the minimum spatial resolution, 5 km, for all GL except Lake Superior, and meets the minimum temporal resolution, 3 hours, for all GL (the Donelan has a 1-hour time resolution) [18]. Despite these shortcomings, the Donelan is the only source of data for waves on the GL that meets the requirement of 10 years of sea state data, provides a suitable source for preliminarily assessing the entirety of the GL wave resource, and can be compared to observations from the nine NDBC buoys providing omni- and directional wave spectral density data.

Furthermore, the three parameters included in the GLCFS Donelan model archive align with the TS guidance in varying degrees. The TS requires the use of the spectrally estimated significant wave height, or characteristic wave height, defined as

$$H_{m0} = 4\sqrt{m_0} \quad (1)$$

The Donelan aligns with the TS guidance for this parameter, calculating the zeroth spectral moment using derived JONSWAP relations [24]. Additionally, the TS outlines the use of a characteristic wave period defined as the energy period,

$$T_e = \frac{m_{-1}}{m_0} \quad (2)$$

whereas the Donelan outputs the peak period, which is the reciprocal of the peak frequency. The TS specifically recommends against using peak period for defining the wave energy resource, as peak period is highly affected by spectral shape. Given the importance of using the mean energy period, T_e , rather than the peak energy period, T_p , for wave power density calculations, the mean energy period was related to peak energy period by a ratio of 0.9. This scaling results in the calculated wave power density in this study being 90% of what it would be if the T_p output by the Donelan was incorrectly used in the deep-water wave power equation. The scaling value of 0.9 was based on a middle value between relations for the JONSWAP spectrum found in [25] and [26] and the findings of [27] for wind waves. Finally, the TS specifies using the direction associated with the maximum directionally resolved wave power. The TS advises against using the peak wave direction (the direction linked with the peak frequency), as these two directions can differ significantly from each other, and peak wave direction does not accurately represent the direction of wave energy dispersion. The Donelan defines wave direction as the direction of the wave momentum vector. The TS does note that directionally resolved power can be omitted from the assessment if no directional information is available. While this study does analyze directional characteristics of wave energy potential on the GL, it does not follow the rigorous criteria outlined by the TS.

The TS does include stipulations for assessments utilizing parameterized sea state data, like that from the Donelan, as opposed to directional wave spectra. The wave power can be estimated if the characteristic wave height, the energy period, and the water depth are known. This estimation can be further simplified if linear deep water wave theory is assumed, removing the necessity of knowing water depth for estimating wave power (though the TS does not recommend the latter simplification). Given that the Donelan assumes linear deep water wave theory, the wave power in this analysis was calculated as

$$J = \frac{\rho g^2}{64\pi} T_e H_s^2 \quad (3)$$

where J is the deep-water omnidirectional wave power in $\text{W}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$, ρ is the density of fresh water taken to be $1000 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$, g is the acceleration due to gravity taken to be $9.81 \text{ m}\cdot\text{s}^{-2}$, T_e is the mean energy wave period based on the Donelan model's peak period in seconds scaled by 0.9, and H_s is the significant wave height in meters from the Donelan model data. Furthermore, we followed the TS's guidance of excluding model grid points with less than 16 meters of water depth (as defined by the Donelan's included bathymetry data) in order to exclude portions of the GL where depth-limited wave breaking can occur during large wave events, which the TS advises for all reconnaissance and feasibility class assessments [18].

3. Results

Applying the recently developed US coastal wave energy classification scheme to the Donelan data and the average deep water omnidirectional wave power over the entire period of record (2009-2020 for Lake Huron and 2006-2020 for the other four GL), over 88% of grid points included in this study for Lakes Erie, Michigan, Ontario, and Superior and 72% of Lake Huron fall into Class III, with the rest of the GL's surface area falling into Class IV. For the average peak period over the entire period of record from the Donelan, all of the GL's surface area falls into Band 1.

Fig. 1 shows a contour plot of the average wave power over the analysis period. Average wave power density typically is higher towards the eastern sides of each GL due to the dominant wind directions; however, monthly trends

Fig. 1. Average Omnidirectional Deep Water Wave Power Density over the Analysis Period. White areas without contours are regions below 16m depth as defined by the GLCFS bathymetry archived with the Donelan in order to conform with the TS [7,8]

Fig. 2. Box Plot of Lake-wide Average Wave Power over the Analysis Period

across the region illustrate the variability in magnitude and location of maximum wave power density for each lake. Fig. 2 shows a box plot of the average wave power over the period of record, further averaged over each Lake's entire surface. Putting the GL in the context of the US coastal wave energy resource is elucidating, as it shows that the majority of the GL surface area falls into Class III for wave power, which 19% of the coastal US falls into (46% falls into Class I). Furthermore, it shows that the GL generally have fast (higher frequency) waves, as they completely fall into the fastest band, Band 1, which only 21% of the coastal US falls into (53% falls into Band 3). Additionally, looking specifically at Fig. 2, we see that the median of the spatially averaged wave power over each Lake's surface falls into Class III for wave power, viz., the median wave power is greater than $1.1 \text{ kW}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$.

Additional comparisons between the GL and coastal US wave environments illustrate seasonal patterns for wave power potential. Wave power increases during winter months and decreases during the summer. There is a clear trend of maximum wave power in November and December, with minimum wave power availability in June and July across the GL. For example, the July average wave power across Lake Superior's surface over the period of record is $0.33 \text{ kW}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$ (Class IV), whereas in December it is $4.3 \text{ kW}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$ (the high end of Class III). While NDBC buoy data provides opportunities for analysis at nine specific locations across the GL, there is essentially no data during winter months when wave power potential is at its highest. Preliminary analysis shows that the Donelan wave model underpredicts wave power during large storms, but overpredicts the power of lower energy sea states. Large late fall and early winter storms which often surge across the GL, such as a Lake Superior storm in October 2018, which caused nearly \$20 million of damage in Duluth, MN [28]. This storm demonstrated the swift nature of waves in the GL, as the wave energy over the two days before the storm, October 7-8, was just $0.06 \text{ MWh}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$ at the location of NDBC buoy 45006 (located in the western portion of Lake Superior), while the wave energy was $1.6 \text{ MWh}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$ over October 10-11. Data from this storm reiterates how the Donelan model tends to underestimate wave power during large storm events when compared to the NDBC buoy within a respective grid cell, as the Donelan predicted a wave energy of $1.3 \text{ MWh}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$ during the storm, an 18% underprediction. The Donelan predicted $0.12 \text{ MWh}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$ during the two days before the storm, double what the buoy observed. Overall, the Donelan's overprediction of the power of low energy seas dominates, leading to an overprediction of wave energy by 19% during buoy deployment over 2006-2020 compared to buoy 45006 observations in that period ($108 \text{ MWh}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$ predicted vs. $91 \text{ MWh}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$ observed). The wave energy potential on the GL does align with PBE application power needs, such as powering ocean observation equipment, among other exciting opportunities [12].

The analysis does provide a look at how the GL can act as a suitable environment for early-stage technology readiness level WEC testing and development. The wave climate on the GL provides a field-based, scaled-model

testing environment with relatively easy and affordable access to substantial maritime infrastructure. Depending on the coastal US location targeted for final deployments, the GL could serve as anywhere from a 1:2 to 1:10 scaled testing ground while removing some additional complexities of coastal US ocean deployments (e.g., saltwater corrosion and risk for extreme events).

4. Conclusion

This analysis represents a necessary first step towards incorporating the GL wave energy resource into the broader US marine energy resource database and will hopefully be a stepping stone toward using the GL as a scaled field laboratory for WECs. In terms of the recently developed coastal US wave energy characterization classes for wave power, the GL wave power potential is largely classified as Class III (Marginal) and peak wave period falls into Band 1, the lowest period band. The eastern portions of the GL have larger wave power potential on average, and late fall and early winter storms cause high wave power potential compared to summer months, e.g., Lake Superior's July average wave power is $0.33 \text{ kW}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$ vs. $4.3 \text{ kW}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$ in December. Though the Donelan is a simplistic and coarse wave model and does not meet the IEC's criteria for the lowest fidelity class of assessment, it does allow systematically comparing the GL wave energy resource to the coastal US in a standardized fashion. Additionally, this analysis demonstrates the necessity of wider data availability and a hindcast with a wave model like WW3 in order to perform a more accurate and comprehensive analysis of the waves on the GL within the near future.

References

- [1] US EPA R 05. Facts and Figures about the Great Lakes. 2015. Available at: <https://www.epa.gov/greatlakes/facts-and-figures-about-great-lakes>. Accessed April 28, 2023.
- [2] Desjardins J. The Great Lakes Economy: The Growth Engine of North America. Vis. Capital. 2017. Available at: <https://www.visualcapitalist.com/great-lakes-economy/>. Accessed August 14, 2023.
- [3] Great Lakes Wind Energy Feasibility Study. NYSERDA. Available at: <https://www.nyserda.ny.gov/great-lakes-wind-feasibility-study>. Accessed January 20, 2023.
- [4] Musial W, Green R, DeMeo E, Cooperman A, Housner S, Marquis M et al. Great Lakes Wind Energy Challenges and Opportunities Assessment.; 2023:NREL/TP-5000-84605, 1968585, MainId:85378.
- [5] Laura Hancock. In 6-1 decision, Ohio Supreme Court approves Icebreaker wind project in Lake Erie. cleveland 2022. Available at: <https://www.cleveland.com/news/2022/08/in-6-1-decision-ohio-supreme-court-approves-icebreaker-wind-project-in-lake-erie.html>. Accessed December 6, 2022.
- [6] Powering the Blue Economy: Exploring Opportunities for Marine Renewable Energy in Maritime Markets. 2022. Available at: <https://www.energy.gov/sites/default/files/2022-07/wpto-pbe-brochure-july2022.pdf>. Accessed April 28, 2023.
- [7] Ahn S, Haas KA, Neary VS. Wave energy resource classification system for US coastal waters. *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* 2019;104:54–68.
- [8] Marine Energy Atlas. Natl. Renew. Energy Lab. Available at: <https://maps.nrel.gov/marine-energy-atlas>. Accessed August 15, 2023.
- [9] US Department of Commerce N. Recent Fitzgerald Research. Available at: https://www.weather.gov/mqt/fitz_research. Accessed August 15, 2023.
- [10] Hultquist TR, Dutter MR, Schwab DJ. Reexamination of the 9–10 November 1975 “Edmund Fitzgerald” Storm Using Today's Technology. *Bull. Am. Meteorol. Soc.* 2006;87(5):607–622.

- [11] Erickson A. Reconstructed Lakewalk section withstands storm. Duluth News Tribune. <https://www.duluthnewstribune.com/weather/reconstructed-lakewalk-section-withstands-storm>. Published October 22, 2019. Accessed August 7, 2023.
- [12] Cavagnaro RJ, Copping AE, Green R, Greene D, Jenne S, Rose D et al. Powering the Blue Economy: Progress Exploring Marine Renewable Energy Integration With Ocean Observations. *Mar. Technol. Soc. J.* 2020;54(6):114–125.
- [13] Branch R, Ticona Rollano F, Cotter E, McVey JR, Cavagnaro RJ, Rigor I. Marine renewable energy for Arctic observations. *Front. Mar. Sci.* 2022;9. Available at: <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fmars.2022.970337>. Accessed August 15, 2023.
- [14] Foteinis S. Wave energy converters in low energy seas: Current state and opportunities. *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* 2022;162:112448.
- [15] Farhadzadeh A, Hashemi MR, Neill S. Characterizing the Great Lakes hydrokinetic renewable energy resource: Lake Erie wave, surge and seiche characteristics. *Energy* 2017;128:661–675.
- [16] Velioglu Sogut D, Farhadzadeh A, Jensen RE. Characterizing the Great Lakes marine renewable energy resources: Lake Michigan surge and wave characteristics. *Energy* 2018;150:781–796.
- [17] Sogut DV, Jensen RE, Farhadzadeh A. Characterizing lake ontario marine renewable energy resources. *Mar. Technol. Soc. J.* 2019;53(2):21–37.
- [18] Marine energy: wave, tidal and other water current converters. Part 101, Wave energy resource assessment and characterization. Edition 1.0. Geneva, Switzerland: International Electrotechnical Commission; 2015.
- [19] Index of /emf/glcfs/NETCDF_Archive. Available at: https://www.glerl.noaa.gov/emf/glcfs/NETCDF_Archive/. Accessed April 28, 2023.
- [20] Schwab DJ, Bennett JR, Lynn EW. A two-dimensional lake wave prediction system. *Environ. Softw.* 1986;1(1):4–9.
- [21] Donelan MA. A simple numerical model for wave and wind stress prediction. Canada Centre for Inland Waters; 1978.
- [22] Schwab DJ, Bennett JR, Liu PC, Donelan MA. Application of a simple numerical wave prediction model to Lake Erie. *J. Geophys. Res.* 1984;89(C3):3586.
- [23] Hodson J, Donelan M. The computational scheme of a numerical model for wave and wind stress prediction. Environment Canada, Canada Center for Inland Waters; 1978. Available at: <https://publications.gc.ca/site/eng/9.882458/publication.html>. Accessed March 3, 2023.
- [24] Liu PC, Schwab DJ, Bennett JR. Comparison of a Two-Dimensional Wave Prediction Model with Synoptic Measurements in Lake Michigan. *J. Phys. Oceanogr.* 1984;14(9):1514–1518.
- [25] Cahill B, Lewis T. WAVE PERIOD RATIOS AND THE CALCULATION OF WAVE POWER.
- [26] DNV-RP-C205: Environmental Conditions and Environmental Loads. 2007.
- [27] Ahn S. Modeling mean relation between peak period and energy period of ocean surface wave systems. *Ocean Eng.* 2021;228:108937.

[28] Andrew Krueger. Duluth: Storm caused \$18.4M in damage. MPR News 2018. Available at: <https://www.mprnews.org/story/2018/10/19/duluth-damage-storm-estimate>. Accessed August 15, 2023.